

Professor John Raven FRS FRSE 1941-2024

Fundamental insights for the origins, evolution and physiology of marine photosynthetic microbes were provided by the theoretical and experimental work of Professor John Raven, who has died aged 82, on the 23rd May, 2024. John's early experimental work on membrane biophysics diversified into the photosynthetic biochemistry, ecophysiology and ecology of algae. Astonishing insight, and interrogation of the broadest sweep of scientific literature, led him to make major theoretical contributions in understanding the origins and future prospects for plant life in marine, terrestrial and (potentially) extraterrestrial worlds.

His work spanned the energetics and carbon accumulation of phytoplankton (as cyanobacterial prokaryotes and then eukaryotic algae) across 2.4 billion years of global history, their influence on major global geochemical and nutritional cycles, and the current threat of ocean acidification associated with global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. He made a major contribution to understanding the regulation of cellular pH in terrestrial plants, as regulated by biophysical and biochemical processes, during the assimilation of inorganic nitrogen. He analysed how the flow of water in the earliest land plants would have been coupled to developing vasculature, as determined from fossilised remnants. He was a most engaging, supportive and humorous colleague- in maintaining connections with a wealth of collaborators, quirky aspects of his current location and activities would be disseminated via postcards to us all from around the world.

A more detailed obituary can be found in *Current Biology* 34, R1–R3, September 9, 2024

A memorial gathering of the 'Raven Clan' was held at the Botanic Garden, University of Dundee, on 6th July 2024, with over 80 attendees representing John's past and present colleagues and friends. We are grateful for support from staff at the Botanic Garden who generously made facilities available for over 80 attendees, as well as financial support from the School of Life Sciences, University of Dundee, and James Hutton Institute.

During preparations for the celebration of John's life, we solicited tributes from colleagues from around the world, and extracts from these are included in this document; in an accompanying document (Raven Clan Gathering powerpoint slideshow), we collated images submitted by friends and family, interspersed with abbreviated comments and tributes

Howard Griffiths (University of Cambridge)

Steve Hubbard (University of Dundee)

Shorter Tributes for John:

Julian Hibberd, on behalf of Department of Plant Sciences (formerly School of Botany), University of Cambridge

We are deeply saddened to hear that Professor John Raven FRS died last week. John was an undergraduate here and obtained his degree in Botany in 1963. He stayed for his PhD with Enid MacRobbie working on membrane transport in giant algal cells. After a brief period as a Demonstrator in our Department, John left to take up a position in Dundee, where he stayed for the rest of his career. His approach to life was unique, his contributions to the careers of others was immense - including a number of us here now (please see the note from Howard below). And, his contributions to knowledge manifold and diverse- spanning biophysics, the physiological limitations for early plant lifeforms, plant nutrition and long distance transport, and above all, aquatic photosynthesis and marine biology.

Howard adds:

John Raven was an extraordinary character- his breadth of knowledge was unrivalled across the plant sciences. He was an inspirational teacher, and generously supported a legion of postgraduate students and post docs, his ideas providing a platform for their future careers (including my own!). John was sociable, with a keen sense of humour which could skewer lofty pretensions, but with the patience to encourage and inform us lesser mortals. Many stories can be told about the seemingly inevitable avalanche of paper across every surface in his office, from which strata a vital document could instantly be recovered; his recall of a specific paper drawn at random from many thousands of diminutive file cards; his pioneering sartorial sense. Ultimately, John's prodigious scientific output represents the mark of a truly original scholar, and his memory will be carried forward by so many of us who were fortunate to have known him

J. Andrew C. Smith University of Oxford

John was a colossus who bestrode the field of botanical science like few people have ever done before. The range and extent of his interests, and the understanding he achieved of so many aspects of biology, were legendary. One moment John could be talking about the finest details of the bioenergetics of photosynthesis (proton-motive Q cycle, anyone?) and then in the next, with equal authority, about the broad sweep of the evolutionary history of land plants (did herbivorous dinosaurs ever consume CAM plants, and how would we know?). John was a polymath who read more widely than most of us could have imagined, wrote cogently and fluently, and broadened and enlightened our horizons.

I first met John in 1977, visiting Dundee and the Aladdin's cave of his departmental office, while I was a graduate student working on the regulation of phloem transport. John was in the middle of producing a brilliant series of papers published in *New Phytologist* on pH regulation, nitrogen assimilation, and long-distance transport. These papers made sense of a huge amount of historical literature on plant growth and mineral nutrition and produced a kind of modern synthesis, showing how these features of plant function could be explained in terms of the latest theories of membrane transport, ion balance and bioenergetics. Out of all the hundreds of papers that John produced subsequently, these remain amongst my favourites – and I still possess the original reprints, worn and dog-eared through frequent use. Looking back, I realize now that these were not only my favourite papers of John's, but amongst my favourite papers in science.

The late 1970s was of course a time before the internet – but this didn't matter too much, as we had John. If something in the literature was confusing, it was possible to rummage around in the library to seek out an answer. But generally it was much more illuminating to ask John. He was like a one-man Wikipedia of plant science, although more so, as his answers would always be provided with a little nugget of context, yielding some further insight into the biological significance of the issue concerned (which, surprisingly frequently, turned out to be something on which John happened to be writing a paper at the time). These answers would often arrive on a postcard, in John's distinctive hand, dispatched from some distant part of the world where he was travelling, but yet still found the time to write at the local airport. Many of us have collections of these postcards, mementos of John's

extraordinary eclecticism and his generosity of spirit, reflections of his vitality and the pleasure he took in discussing the most far-flung and diverse topics in biology.

We will miss John terribly, but we still have his work – and it will be with us forever.

Dianne Edwards, University of Cardiff

Thank you, John-- for the kindly friendship and wisdom that I have been privileged to share over many, many years and for your enormous contributions to our scientific community.

John Beardall, Monash University

I was lucky enough to get the chance to start work as a post-doc for John Raven in January 1979 – amazing really given my ignominious start when I was an hour late to my interview because I didn't take the exact train John recommended (I was to find out later that amongst other things John had a prodigious knowledge of train routes and timetables!). Such was my start on a journey that would see me in his lab for ~ 3.5 years and a further 42 years of collaboration and friendship.

Working for John was a revelation. How could he know so much about so many things? The sight of him churning out paper after paper on his typewriter (this was after all 1979, before the advent of personal computers) was daunting to a young post-doc, but once you got the idea that John was just operating at a different level to most of us it was much easier! I remember the many sessions in 'The Tav' where, over a pint or 3 of heavy, John would cover beer mats with jottings of ideas – to be followed the next day by a draft paper.

The breadth of John's knowledge was exceptional. His work covered the full gamut of topics from cellular energetics and ion transport through to evolution and astrobiology, and his extensive list of collaborators across the world is testament to his willingness to share his ideas and inspire a whole new generation of graduate students. John spent a lot of his time travelling to visit with colleagues and attend meetings – an enduring memory for me is the way he would always have a stack of postcards when travelling, which he would then send off to all and sundry. The patter of his postcards through letterboxes finally gave way to emails, but we would still get an update of where John was and what he was doing!

Sir Isaac Newton wrote, "If I have seen further, it is by standing on the shoulders of giants", but John towered over us, and his passing has left the world a poorer and certainly less interesting place. We will miss him terribly.

John and Howard add:

John reminded me of " his house in West Ferry, where the walls were cracking under the weight of books on the shelves and the front garden was clearly an early experiment in re-wilding".... And the evenings at 4 Pennan Grove spent listening to vinyl records of Tom Lehrer and Beyond the Fringe.... And not only his knowledge of the train timetable, but also every possible aircraft overhead, topped up by his annual pilgrimage to the Leuchars Air Show.

Ali Roberts, Class of 1994

I was one of John's undergraduate students in Diabolical Sciences (as we called it), and he was also my university supervisor when I did my PhD at SCRI. I'm going to talk not about his science, but as a teacher and mentor.

As an undergrad in 1990 I remember John running between the rotating blackboards in the large MSI lecture theatre, scribbling diagrams, or sometimes using the overhead projector; he drove the secretaries mad with his habit of photocopying algal fronds onto acetates to use in lectures. John was in his black kilt phase (the Raven tartan; black checks on a black background) or a skirt with a lacy underskirt peeping out, often teamed with running shoes or hiking boots. He had a selection of T-shirts that either had the logo of a recent botanical conference, or some witty science-related cartoon or slogan. He'd come into the lecture theatre and peel off his sweatshirt to reveal that day's T-shirt, knowing that we were all waiting to see what it said.

JAR's undergraduate lectures could be pretty dense, often requiring extra reading to really understand them, but I was lucky; I managed to follow his rambling, expansive lecturing style and somehow knew which facts had to be written down to answer exam questions and which information was more "icing on the cake". You didn't need to be in his company for long to understand how dedicated he was to his science and teaching. He was an excellent communicator with a wonderful (if sometimes obscure) sense of humour.

John's office was legendary. He curated the most incredible stratified filing system; papers from floor to ceiling, engulfing furniture. At least once while I was an undergraduate he had an avalanche and news spread through the department as if it was a serious geological event!

I'd go to his office to ask one question. He'd answer that question but then ask me another one or two... Always probing what I knew, if he could suggest some extra reading, maybe pass on a titbit of information from a new publication to encourage me off in a new direction. He'd dive, sometimes multiple times, into the piles of papers, riffling through manuscripts and envelopes, the strata divided with newspapers to provide timestamps in the depths. He might sometimes stop to stroke his beard, chin-down, and utter a hmmh as he considered his next move. He might unearth some dried, flat-pressed algal fronds, a bag of decomposing ex-field trip samples or an old sandwich in the process. I also recall welly boots, socks, hats (he seemed to love hats), cheese, newspapers, running shorts, a bird's nest and bottles in the strata. BUT, in a remarkably short time, considering the utter chaos that appeared to surround him, he'd triumphantly slide out a photocopy or reprint and hand it to me. Sometimes I'd be handed several... Sometimes I'd leave his office ruefully thinking that I hadn't really asked to be given "all this stuff". BUT, I always left his office with new thoughts and a feeling that I should go off and do some more reading. His enthusiasm was infectious.

John ALWAYS spoke to me as an equal and that, I've realised, was an incredibly precious and powerful thing. He felt I could do science, so I should try. I could never understand why John was so kind, so encouraging. You knew you were in the presence of a great intellect, and the fact that he brushed that off and spoke to me as though I was smart enough to keep up (even if I most definitely was not) made me feel empowered. This attitude wasn't just at work either. I knew John and Linda personally because I had a relationship with their son for a while and they were both extremely kind to me. John sent me a birthday card for a number of years and there was always a thoughtful message in it, plus something like a riddle... There would be an abstruse comment that somehow linked the nationality of the painter of the illustration on the card and a photosynthetic metabolite... I almost always had to go back and ask him to explain the link that his big brain had seen and that he thought I'd understand too... When I came out of my PhD viva I hadn't seen him for a few weeks but there he was, waiting in the lab with a card and a bottle of champagne in his hand. Lovely

John. I'll not forget his kindness and I know he thought about and cared about his students and lab members a great deal.

We students, also talked and thought about John quite a bit. In the early 90s it was definitely unusual to have a transvestite lecturer. John's combination of skirts, visible underskirts and a big grey beard proclaimed loudly and proudly that he didn't care what anyone thought of him. Whether in a lecture theatre, at home or walking through the city centre he was comfortable in his own mind and his own attire. To undergraduates in particular that was a powerful message; young people trying to figure themselves out had a brilliant role model in John and the city largely took him to its heart which makes me proud. The cartoon of him (you can see in the slideshow) that appeared in the Dundee Courier during freshers week in 1999 has been pinned to the board in my office ever since. He taught me and many others that being different is cool, following your heart is valid, living an unusual life can be very rewarding and being tolerant of others is hugely important.

Those of us lucky enough to have been taught by John will remember it all our lives. He's had a huge impact on many generations of students in sharing his unique thinking, and indeed changing the way we think. He greatly enriched my life and many others and I'd like to think has shaped my own science, teaching and students. John Albert Raven is someone to give thanks for, and a life worth celebrating.

Thanks for everything John. Cheers!
Allie

Andrew (FA) Smith (University of Adelaide) (see extended tribute and songs)

Musical Memories of John Raven: Silly scientific songs (1970s) from my as-yet unpublished songbook

Preamble

I started singing at my Grammar (High) School at Heversham, UK, and then joined a male-voice choir. I didn't seriously continue when I went to Cambridge but re-started in the lab. (solo) when doing my PhD there. John Raven joined in when he started one year later – usually clad in a suit, of course with a lab. coat when doing experiments. We used to swap sung lines or verses over the low partition between our two desks in small adjoining carrels in the lab., also with benches on which we did short-term experiments with radioisotopes – there were no separate offices. 'Health & Safety' concerns involved use of hand-held Geiger counters. We had manual radiation counters for dried algal samples and stop-watches, so there was plenty of time for musical composition as well as science talk. Our PhD supervisor Enid Macrobbie usually only expressed displeasure when she was giving small-group tutorials in her lab./office, separated only by a non-soundproof partition. She used to come out, put her hands on her hips and sigh – that signal was enough for us to stop singing. John Banfield, Enid's young technician, who had a chair next to a bench just beside Enid's lab./office, occasionally expressed displeasure (as I recall). He died a few months ago and it is a tragedy that he isn't around to give his memories of 'boys behaving badly'. I have no idea what Enid really thought. At least one other inhabitant who shall remain nameless couldn't stand it and Enid moved him to another lab./office.

Songs

Tunes that we used for composition of lyrics were mostly well known at the time. I think the original lyrics can all now be found on Google. Sadly, the original ones have mostly not

survived, although many were later modified and used by me if not by John, written on menus, beer mats and the like, and saved: hence this account.

C Barry Osmond Canberra

Vale John Raven: recollections from Barry Osmond and Cornelia Büchen-Osmond

For this stumbling antipodean in the Botany School Cambridge UK 1966-67 it was a treat to take a glass of cider with Tom apRees' court in the pub at day's end and there to meet John Raven, then one of Enid MacRobbie's team of astonishingly sharp aspirants in plant biology.

John and I met often during a later sabbatical in the UK in 1980 when, memorably, he explained that if one hoped to understand boundary-layer effects on $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ fractionation in submerged aquatic plants, more accurate stream water flow rates would be obtained with an orange than with a pooh stick!

John was already a frequent visitor to Australia as we sat together at the International Botanical Congress in Sydney (1981) and speculated on the absence of stomata in cuticles of fossilised early land plants during an authoritative plenary.

John Keeley overheard our discussion and immediately volunteered a field excursion to the high Andes of Peru that was worth every bit of the headaches from shovel work in peat at 4500 metres elevation (and the cover photo for)

Keeley, J.E., Osmond, C.B., Raven, J.A. (1983) *Nature* 310, 694-695

Stylites, a vascular land plant without stomata absorbs CO_2 via its roots.

(John Keeley's wife Stirling had the last word: "How does Stylites CAM-peat?")

John Raven was the preeminent Polymath of our discipline;
plant biology world wide is the poorer today for his passing

Dear Linda: our sincere, deepest sympathy; our thoughts are with you.

We are sorry that the Biosphere 2 adventure was prematurely truncated:

you and John would have hugely stimulated plant biology at Columbia.

Fortunately, U Arizona Tucson is keeping the facility active with support from the owner of the facility and the EU Research Council

Jane Wishart (University of St Andrews)

I was thinking about the first time I met John and Linda – in Glen Prosen around 1985 or 1986. My son, then age 5 or 6 came running in telling me he had found a man, with a big white beard, lying down outside looking at our moss. I told him to invite the man in for a coffee which he duly did and thus trips to the coffee shop began. It was a strange coincidence that, after finishing my degree, I applied for a job Linda advertised in the Dundee Courier! - my very first academic position I am also aware that all through my time,

as an undergraduate and a postgraduate and beyond to my time at St Andrews, John was there, gently encouraging, sending post cards from everywhere in the world and answering email questions, usually by return. When I got my job at St Andrews, John sent such a lovely post card which arrived on my desk in my first week. It read “ dear Jane, Sorry you are leaving SCRI, but the St Andrews position seems to be a great opportunity for you – enjoy it! I’ll drop in when I’m in St Andrews” I still have this of course and it has a Kiwi on the front!

What a thing to do – to think to write and welcome me to my new job! And indeed, we did have many lunches at the Dolls House over the years I was teaching there. I always took John for a nice lunch before he came to talk to my students about “Peak P”!

The thing is, I do not think for one minute I was special in any way – John had time for people - I can only assume he was more or less constantly writing to someone about something and encouraging everyone along the way . I am so very lucky I was able to spend some great times with him and was able to listen to him talk to the students and floor them, of course , with his unbelievable knowledge and his unrivalled wit! Hilarity always ensued and the class usually went on way beyond the 5pm finish.

Mike Ferguson, Regius Professor of Life Sciences, University of Dundee

When I arrived in Dundee in 1988 John and I were affiliated to different departments but overlapped at seminars and so on. From the first moment he was extremely generous and kind to me, showing interest in what I did and always being among the first to send a card of congratulation if I received some accolade. I was in awe of his scientific prowess and impact, not least in marine algal carbon recycling – a topic never more important than now. I, and many others, found him truly inspiring in making science so societally (in his case planetary) relevant. I think Dundee Life Sciences has remained true to John’s philosophy of science with impact, and his inspirational example is deeply etched into our collective DNA. I am proud and enriched to have known him. I offer my sincere condolences to his family and friends.

Howard Fallowfield, Flinders University:

He was a titan, who generously shared ideas and insight with colleagues and students, often spiked with a brilliant sense of humour.

I have very fond memories of time spent at Dundee with John at his fabulously generous summer parties, crazy garden events at our cottage at Monikie and in the Tav & the Campbelltown bar. He also stirred staid Adelaide when he attended conferences there!

Sinead Collins, University of Edinburgh

I miss him. The guy literally phoned Montreal in 2003 when he got my first paper to review, and spent hours on the phone walking me through how a CCM worked. HOURS. ON A PHONE. Then he answered all my crazy questions for years. Then he helped supervise my first grad student (Elisa Schaum)

Kevin Flynn, Plymouth Marine Laboratories (exerpt from a more detailed tribute0

Co-authoring with John was at once a revelation and a frustration. His incredible knowledge span and his ability for lateral thought, and indeed random insertion of thoughts running off

at tangents, made the whole task an education.... And that, in some ways, was the hallmark of John, an ability to weave disparate strands of information together. Whether that was for his own intellectual enjoyment or for everyone else's edification I was never quite sure. It could be a real challenge keeping up with John,.... to try and follow the journey of his thought processes.

David Beerling, University of Sheffield

very sad to hear of John's death, not only a truly brilliant intellect but also a great supporter of younger scientists, including me, back in the day. (he was elected to the RS the same year as David Read, 'the class of 1990' they called themselves)

Kunshan Gao, Xiamen University

I am sorry to hear the sad news of John Raven's passing, and would like to express my deepest condolences

Bernd Wollenweber University of Aarhus

I had just finished my PhD in Vienna and had been contacted by John (a letter in those days!) asking for a copy of my very first paper. He also asked if I knew anybody interested to do a postdoc with him. I answered immediately (by phone) that I would be very interested, and we agreed on a date for an interview in Dundee.

The flight from Vienna to Edinburgh went fine, but the bus from the airport to the train station had an accident. Thus I arrived late at Dundee station, but John was still there – holding a sign with my surname. He said he didn't mind waiting because he went to a pub and met very interesting people there – would I like to meet them? Of course I replied. We had a pint; the pub was full of punks – and I didn't understand a word of their conversation 😊

Thereafter, John invited me home, Linda made dinner – and that was the interview. The next day I was shown the lab, and after a trip to the botanical garden John offered me the job - and I started to work a couple of months later.

Peter Grubb University of Cambridge

A brief message from Peter Grubb on interaction with John Raven

Like all his friends I think of John always finding the funny side to an issue or situation, but today I draw attention only to two of our scientific exchanges.

Firstly a case where he kindly encouraged me.

I was grateful to John for showing a genuine interest in a paper by me published in the *New Phytologist* in 1970 reporting morphological and physiological studies on *Haplomitrium* and *Takakia*, and arguing that they are hepatics with roots.

Only somebody with John's range of interests and expertise would have noticed the paper which has been generally ignored.

The next overlap in interests gave me a chance to help John. In his penetrating paper asking how small can a viable seed be, eventually published in *Functional Ecology* in 1999 John initially assumed that the plants not dependent on micro-organisms to become established (as in the case of orchids) and producing the smallest seeds are light-demanding, In this he followed the mass of authors since Salisbury's classic book of 1941. Luckily the paper was sent to me as a referee at the time when a research student of mine (Dan Metcalfe) and I were working on tiny-seeded shade-tolerant species of trees, shrubs

and herbs in tropical lowland rainforest in Singapore. The species we found with the lightest seeds was *Sonerila heterostemon* in the Melastomataceae, a strongly shade-tolerant herb which becomes established on steep, moist, litter-free slopes. The mean dry mass was only 0.0050 mg. John welcomed this re-orientation in thinking, and the paper was revised before acceptance by Functional Ecology. It was a great pleasure to interact with John in both cases.

Not many experts on the goings-on within plant cells master in addition the evolution of whole plant organs and disseminules. Here's a hope that there will continue to be such people in the future!

Jim Moroney, Louisiana State University

John Raven was better than Google – Before internet searches, I would occasionally ask John a question about algal physiology. An example might be “What is known about bicarbonate uptake in Chrysophytes?” Not only would I get a reply with references answering my question, but he would also send me “related” articles that he felt might be helpful. His knowledge of the literature was unsurpassed, and he managed to integrate seemingly unrelated articles in meaningful ways.

Steve Long, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

John used his encyclopedic knowledge to produce a string of novel insights across plant sciences, yet despite being head and shoulders above the rest of us, was incredibly modest and seemed to always have time for others and give very serious thought and advice on the problems we were tackling, as I first discovered as a first semester graduate student.

Alyson Tobin, Edinburgh Napier University

I will raise a glass and think of John and all his many friends. I was fortunate enough to teach alongside John on a joint MRes we ran at St Andrews- happy memories of the two of us traipsing around St Andrews with a huddle of students while John talked about N fluxes in and out of the sea and I tried to chip in a few random thoughts while marvelling at his amazing memory for facts and figures

Euan Nisbet RHUL

John was... one of those rare kind folk who managed to make science fun and to make the world interesting.

Kaj Sand-Jensen, University of Copenhagen

He is likely the UK-scientist that I have cited most frequently over the years.

I have met him twice – the first time at the meeting in Hull, where I also met you and Howard for the first time, and the second time at the international congress on algae in Copenhagen some years later, where he was treated rather badly by the American chairman following his, John's presentation of inorganic carbon use in algae before a large audience. The chairman wanted to quickly proceed after the presentation, although there was sufficient time for questions and discussions. I used the opportunity to ask questions etc., also because I sensed a hostile tone from the chairman.

Later I met constructive and helpful evaluation in some anonymous reviews which I suspect were written by John.

Jonathan Weyers, University of Dundee

JAR was a true great, an authentic genius. Proud to have published with him. One paper was the result of a very brief conversation with John in his office, re flower structure. It set off a light bulb in his head and only a few days later he presented me with a draft of 'Significance of epidermal fusion and intercalary growth for angiosperm evolution', Trends in Plant Science 2001, 6, 111-113. My only real contributions were the initial chat and a couple of manuscript suggestions! (Another paper was the other way round).

Ben Long University of Newcastle NSW

Very sad to hear of John's passing. His contributions to the CCM field are immense.

Jodi Young University of Washington

John was my external examiner for my DPhil thesis and continued to support me through my career. He was an amazing person and will be sorely missed.

Sven Kranz Rice University

I have very fond memories of him over the years. What a great person and amazing colleague.

David Read, Sheffield University

It is hard to contemplate a botanical world-perhaps any world-without him. What a person! Over the years, one of his 'signature' activities involved the sending of post cards-from all corners of the globe-normally from venues of leading international conferences. These were always jovial in spirit-and uplifting in content. As it happens we were both elected to RS in the same year-1990- and we used to refer to each other, jokingly, as 'the Class of '90'!

Lynn Robertson (now Kerr), class of 1994.

Prof Raven, unique and special in so many ways but most surely the only man with his own bird nest, in his Uni office, at the top of a pile of newspapers! Thank you for sharing your love of botany and for the fun memories of the BSI.

Alison Roberts, class of 1994 and JHI colleague

John was my professor as an undergraduate and became a friend and mentor. He was the most impressive mind I've ever experienced and I'm so grateful to have known him. He was an inspiring and admirable teacher; I'll remember him bouncing between and frantically scribbling on the multiple blackboards in the MSI lecture theatre and enthusiastically leading field trips to hillsides, woods and rocky shores. A kind and thoughtful man, always interesting and often amusing company. A formidable scientist. I knew the power of his intellect but he always spoke to me as an equal; powerful indeed! He also taught me that being different is cool, following your heart is valid and living an unusual life can be hugely rewarding. Definitely someone to give thanks for, and a life worth celebrating. You hugely enriched my life John. Thank you, Allie.

Lisa Smolenska (class of 1995)

He was an amazing man. His lectures are forever imprinted in my mind. A character, a contributor, a brilliant, rare mind and a curator of the most amazing paper "strata" filing system I've ever witnessed.

Karl Abel

In a lifetime, you do not meet many like John. If you are lucky enough to be taught by him you remember it all your life. If you have the great good fortune to talk with him and work with him then it changes the way you think for the remainder of your life, for the better. He is a sad loss to this world.

Dr Keith Skene University of Dundee

Such sad news. An amazing man - so brilliant yet so communicative with a wonderful sense of humour. Who can forget the Rubisco washing powder advert or the black and white acetates of algae that he would place on the glass plate and press copy! It used to drive the secretary mad. He has had such an impact on so many generations of students and we all owe him so much in sharing his unique thinking with us. As one of his former PhD students, he had such a massive impact on my own thinking and teaching and still does. Rest well.

David Leader

Very sad news. I also have fond memories of him and Linda from my time at Dundee Uni., Diabolical Sciences.

Dale Sanders University of York

John's encyclopaedic knowledge and original thinking was an inspiration to so many plant biologists. A particular landmark for me was his seminal work on control of cytoplasmic pH - something he worked with F Andrew Smith on and which set the framework in the late 1970s for much of the research I performed as a post-doc. John attained guru status for many in the plant membrane transport community but never lost the friendliness and sense of humour that would always put people at ease.

And talking of putting people at ease, here's a story from my PhD viva where John was my external examiner. Referring to something that he obviously knew was a mis-print, he said during my viva:

"Did you work with a particularly smelly new gas?"

"No!???" I was thinking: "what on earth is he talking about?"

"Oh, I just wondered about BO₂ on page XX - whether this is some new boron compound or something".

We then had a really good laugh, knowing that CO₂ was meant. That exchange characterised the rest of the viva: some really very serious and challenging chats about my project interspersed with humour and banter. I couldn't have wished for a better experience at this critical phase of my scientific life.

I hope that the Raven Gathering manages to convey the deep respect we all have for John as well as the fun he conveyed to those with whom he did science.

Willie Wilson, University of Plymouth, and on behalf of the Marine Biological Association, Plymouth

John, you have certainly left a mark on marine biologists worldwide and to the Marine Biological Association MBA specifically; we truly appreciate your service to the MBA where

you served as the Royal Society Governor and MBA Trustee for 22 years, 1993-96; 2000-03; 2005-08; 2009-2022, always positive, constructive and insightful with an understanding on pretty much every topic we covered. You were a fabulous mentor to all our Fellows, but most of all we always enjoyed your cheerful company. Personally, I remember as a young postdoc I was to look out for you at a meeting to quiz you on physiology of virus infections of marine algae; I didn't know if I would recognise you, but my supervisor at the time (and old friend of yours, Noel Carr, now also dearly departed) said: "just think of what a character from the old testament would look like with a black skirt"! That first meeting was certainly memorable, you started by saying you knew very little about viruses but still proceeded to present me with an incredibly detailed (and as it turned out accurate) overview of the physiological changes an algal cell would experience during a virus infection.

May your molecules and memories be forever with us.

RIP my friend and mentor

Peter von Dassow, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

on behalf of Jane Wong, Osvaldo Ulloa, Juan Diego Gaitan Espitia

We were very happy when John agreed to join our eclectic group of co-authors to analyze a mystery of the disappearance of phytoplankton from where they'd be expected to thrive. What surprised us was how, whenever the first author Jane sent a new draft, comment, or question, John was always the fastest to respond, always with valuable insight, and suggesting the most relevant papers, whether from the latest literature or from key early work from the 1970s that would have been very difficult for us to find. As the greatest mind in algal photosynthesis, surely he had a lot of more prestigious demands on his time, but he clearly made it a priority to encourage us, gently guide us away from some conceptual errors, and, most of all, to offer his genius to support a junior scientist he'd never even met. He was always there for anyone who needed him, whether it was an editor, a senior PI, a postdoc or a student, offering his brilliant, energetic and ever-young mind. We will always remember how his genius reflected a love of his science that was expressed with incredible generosity.

Tracy Lawson, University of Essex

One of my first encounters with John Raven was at my PhD board meeting (or whatever they were called then) as John was my board member (or whatever they were called then). I walked into his office that was stacked with papers, and I remember thinking why does he have such a small office for such an eminent professor. His desk and rest of the floor space were stacked full of papers with no room to work, so John was using the pull-out stationary drawer to do written work. The only space that seemed to be free was the sink. He asked all the usual questions of how I was getting on with my first year of my PhD, to which I said fine. I then asked him a question about a paper I had been reading and something I did not understand - and he said 'ahhhh' - and threw his hand into a pile of papers that was standing floor to ceiling, and like pulling an ace from the pack of cards, he pulled out the paper in question to start explaining it to me. I was amazed not only by the fact that he knew everything but how he magically pulled out this paper from the thousands in the stack. I said to him 'never mind the question - how did you do that?'...to which he just gave a small smile and he continued to discuss the science. I encountered John many times during my PhD often socially, when he always had wine on Friday night in his lab - which I would join, although was not a member of his lab, but he would generously include me. As time grew

so did the paper piles in his office and by my 2nd year John had migrated to work only on the sink draining board as this now was the only space left. Towards the end of my PhD there was the famous “John Raven office clearance” (I think for safety reasons) – so the next time I entered his room I realized that he had a huge office that spanned a vast floor space that had been hidden by even more papers than I had originally envisaged.

John was an amazing scientist and generous person, who inspired numerous ECRs many of whom have remained in the field and developed independent careers and labs. His wealth of knowledge and depth of subject is demonstrated by the fields he covered, with topics ranging from cells to space, cyanobacteria to algae, and higher plants. As current president of the Society of Experimental Biology I would like to acknowledge his contribution to the SEB, not only to science and greatly advancing our understanding of the research topics that span our society, animal, cell and plant but also his contribution to developing the society as an active member attending the majority of annual meetings, organizing sessions, satellites and for the numerous talks he presented. John was greatly appreciated and will be greatly missed. I am sorry that I am unable to attend the Gathering of the Raven Clan but I am currently at the annual SEB meeting in Prague, however, I would like to say thank you for everything John.

Fiona King (undergraduate 1995, Ecology)

I saw that you were one of the contacts and I decided to drop you a line to say what an impact Professor Raven had on me as on so many others. He was the second supervisor (or something like that) for my final year undergraduate research project with Ali Blackwell. This was a duty that he could have taken pretty lightly. Instead he showed a genuine interest in my work, inviting me to come and speak to him about it several times, asking incredibly insightful questions and sharing his views. It was a bit scary being one on one with someone with such a huge brain but he made it easy for me!

His office was, of course, quite something! Piles of papers everywhere! The like an academic's office out of a cartoon. And then he did an amazing thing. He started speaking about a paper that he thought would be relevant and of interest and he went to one of the piles of papers and he pulled it out of the middle. Maybe it was a clever trick, maybe it wasn't, but that moment stayed with me. AND I read the paper - AND he was right, it was interesting and relevant!

I often struggled to follow Professor Raven's lectures but he taught me so much in those individual sessions, and he also showed all of us what it is to be genuinely yourself and absolutely unique. I never forgot him and speak about him often. My partner is an academic and he was very excited when he got to see Professor Raven at a conference because he knew what a figure he was in Dundee!

Juliet Brodie Natural History Museum

John was a truly remarkable person in so many ways. He was a brilliant scientist and dedicated to serving the psychological community right to the last. He was also a highly valued friend and always generous with his time. A great correspondent on a wealth of topics, ask John a scientific question and a stimulating discussion would ensue. And in my office are the many post cards that he sent over the years, a lovely reminder of the care he

took to stay in touch. He will be greatly missed by so many but his legacy and contribution to science will remain and for that we can celebrate.

Stephen Maberly CEH Lancaster

John was an extraordinary scientist and person. He had an exceptional interest, knowledge and insight into a huge range of topics- including some unusual ones such as the wingspan of different types of aircraft! I am very grateful to have been able to work with John: he was a generous collaborator and extremely kind and I learnt a lot from him. John's contribution to many aspects of research will be long-lasting.

Hans Lambers UWA

What impressed me most about John was his encyclopaedic knowledge. A good encyclopedia does not simply contain a lot of information, but has that information organised in specific sections with numerous cross references to other relevant sections. That is also how John's brain functioned, in my experience. When I asked John to read one of my papers, he would often add a new dimension that I had not considered, and I would then offer him a co-authorship. The best example is our Marschner review (Lambers et al. 2010), in which John pointed out the quantitatively important contribution of ribosomal RNA to leaf phosphorus concentrations. That laid the foundation for a very fruitful collaboration with Mark Stitt's group (Lambers et al. 2012; Sulpice et al. 2014).

During the last few months, we were collaborating on a manuscript on the growth rate hypothesis (Elser et al. 2003; Elser et al. 2010). Plant ecologists are very keen on using this hypothesis to explain scaling relations in terrestrial plants, involving leaf nitrogen and phosphorus concentrations (Kerkhoff et al. 2006). In John's and my view, this hypothesis makes no sense when it comes to mature leaves of plants, because these leaves stopped growing. Together with Daniil Scheifes we were working towards an alternative explanation to explain the findings on scaling of nitrogen and phosphorus. If we can retrieve text John wrote from his laptop, he will end up as a co-author on our opinion paper. If that turns out impossible, we will dedicate our paper to him, because we have been discussing this topic over a glass of wine on numerous occasions over the years, when John stayed at our place in Australia.

Charles Cockell, University of Edinburgh

John was a very remarkable scientist. As well as having a brilliant mind which seemed to be able to grasp the most complex subjects in biology (and quantify them), he always had a broad set of interests mixed in with his generous and thoughtful personality. Not least he always had time to communicate and show an interest. It was not uncommon to get emails from John about subjects or papers he had discovered, thoughts he had, or new ideas he had stumbled across that cut across everything from plankton, plants and planets. He really was a quite unique and extraordinary person and will be very much missed.

Davide Bulgarelli (University of Dundee)

I shared with John what was my very first office as an independent scientist in Dundee. Few days before starting I was told he had to move "few" papers to clear a desk...

...I couldn't imagine how many! Soon though it wasn't the volume of material impressing me. Rather, John's capacity of "pulling" a given manuscript from that apparent chaos to inspect a 'Figure 1b'... This was a lesson I remember to these days: a new appointment does not

necessarily define you as a scientist; a profound understanding of science, starting from your very own, does.

Rod Herbert, University of Dundee

I still have happy memories of working with him on the Annual Field Course at Ardeonaig. His enthusiasm was infectious and his knowledge encyclopedic but he always gave the impression to the students that what they had found was something new and exciting. That was his magic. He will be greatly missed.

(Contact Addresses on core mailing list)

Katharine Preedy

My memories of John are of an enveloping warmth, generosity of spirit and personal interest together with a sense of endless possibility. He was a wonderful source of inspiration and advice. I was completing my PhD just as he started to think seriously about astrobiology, to which end he decided a physical map of the university was a necessity and he clicked print on that job a couple of minutes before I clicked print on my thesis. The departmental printers were out of action for 3 months and I had to go elsewhere to get the thesis printed. Thankfully, as my internal examiner he was understanding of the delay, and he got his revenge by getting absorbed in a discussions with my external examiner before my viva. After 40 minutes I went to his office to enquire whether we were going to meet, and he apologised saying they had been confabulating about the impact of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current on the jet stream and they'd be with me in 15 minutes. Needless to say, on arrival at the viva he had the entire thesis at his fingertips and a philosophical grasp of the focus of the work. Somehow, it seemed to encapsulate his ability to direct his attention completely and with kindness on the matter in hand, but always with a sparkle in his eye.

Nigel Kerby, JHI

I first met John when I was a PhD student studying the composition of pyrenoids at Leeds University and he was an external examiner for phycology PhD students around 1975. While a Research Fellow at Leeds and about to start a new job in Professor WDP Stewart's AFRC Cyanobacterial Research Group we were invited to write a book chapter for Advances in Botanical Research. Consequently, Bill Stewart used to introduce me to his visitors as his Post-Doc that was really working for John Raven. I got to experience John's style of writing and remember having to remind him that we were writing one article not the complete volume! At this time, John's outstanding information retrieval was apparent - we were at a party at his house of the Abroath Road and I happened to ask if he knew the author of Picnic at Hanging Rock, first thing the next morning after a very late night I found a copy of the book in my pigeon-hole!

I had the pleasure to be with John for a conference and a "significant" birthday of his in a very small rural village. We went out for drinks with Linda and others and John arrived at the bar wearing the "Raven" tartan kilt, sandals (no socks) and a white T-shirt emblazoned with an image of Linda. Drivers were so distracted by John that one mounted a pavement narrowly missing the neatly aligned, empty cafe chairs. That night there was a real "buzz" in that chosen bar.

It was such an honour and immense pleasure to have known and worked with John, a remarkable scientist with an immense diverse knowledge coupled with kindness and humility.

David Hopkins SRUC

I think Ali said all the things many of us could have said with different examples but with less style than Ali. Here's a gentle reflection from John given to an early career academic seeking research grants:

"Think about whether you need to write a proposal or just think harder"

Brian Eddy, University of Dundee

Yes I remember the 3D deep litter filing system and the precision burrowing to immediately locate the reference. As a recently appointed lecturer I was working on ideas for a research project and it was suggested a good way forward would be to seek John's advice. As was often the way, the discussion took place in the main corridor. John quickly identified the main point and went on to expand in depth and in detail on a Zoology topic where I was supposed to be the expert!!! I was very humbled and recognised John, even as a Botanist (ed.: hrrrrmmmmph!), he was a true polymath.

Roy Oliver, University of Dundee

I started in the Dept the same time as John. We each gave a short outline of our research areas in the long wooden hut the Dept was housed. His talk, which I could not understand, was full of words to describe very small quantities of Biological entities.

As you will recall his small office was heaped with finished newspapers until removed as a Fire hazard. He used to walk to work possibly on medical advice to get more exercise before acquiring his distinctive Triumph* car. At his parties he sometimes sported an Aussie outback hat with dangling corks to ward off flies. He occasionally wore highly distinctive union jack themed socks at staff meetings. As you know he only occasionally went to the Tavern 'after work' before returning to his Office to continue work. What a lot of wasters the rest of us were.

(*HG adds- one of my contemporaries was hitching to Edinburgh and was picked up by John in the convertible Triumph Herald... his hair became caught in the sticky tape used to hold the roof together!)

Bruce Osborne, UCD Dublin

...during a field course to Millport with students from Dundee: The local pub to which we naturally adjourned every night (could have been the Newton Bar) had an old style jukebox with records dating back to the late 70's early 80's. We took it in turns to 'feed' the jukebox and when it came to John's turn (after not that much persuasion actually) we were regaled with 'Total Eclipse of the Heart' and 'Lost in France'. Who would have guessed that John was a Bonnie Tyler fan? Of course everyone then played Bonnie Tyler records for the rest of the week!

Colin Osborne, University of Sheffield

John was an inspiring scientist, fun to hang out with, and tremendously supportive and kind when I was starting out on my fellowship. Funnily enough we've just used his paper on the relationship between guard cell size and stomatal function to interpret data in a new paper imminent in PC&E. A classic Raven approach to a problem.

Jennifer Carfrae

My earliest memory of John was as my 1st year Biology lecturer, and he continued to support me through a range of ecology subjects through my undergraduate degree studies. I have some wonderful memories of him lobbing melons and pineapples into the lecture theatre like rugby balls when discussing reproduction methods in plants, and of course his miraculous filing system which I seem to have inherited (moving rooms is a mission itself!).

I was thrilled to discover that he was a co-supervisor with Dr Lucy Sheppard of a PhD in plant ecophysiology that I applied for. During the interview process we were unexpectedly taken out to the field site where John found it highly amusing that I was plodding around a peatland in a pair of platform knee high boots! However, I was extremely grateful to be offered the PhD despite this, and have the opportunity to work with John and Lucy over the following 4 years. I looked forward to his regular postcard updates on his travels and our quarterly meetings in Edinburgh.

His patience and guidance during my PhD were vastly appreciated and his enthusiasm for the subject infectious! As one of the most medically difficult periods in my life, he was a rock, and his sense of humour kept me going. His legacy will continue for years to come in his publications, but he will be missed. In the words of my friend from my undergraduate degree Alasdair Ross: "John Raven - he was a legend!". I know this sentiment is felt across my graduating year group of 2000.

Lucy Sheppard

My first meeting with John was when I was an Honours student at Aberdeen. The biological society had invited this, even then, 1975, revered scientist to talk to us. Normally only the chairman got to have dinner with the guest speaker but I volunteered to cook so all the committee got to meet this wonderful man. He was most appreciative and very entertaining. Obviously it was his first visit to the zoology department as when he had trouble with getting the lights etc to work he said "I guess this is the intelligence test I need to pass before you allow me to speak!". Our paths didn't cross again for a long time but as I became more focussed on N it was possibly inevitable I would be asking him question after question. It was so refreshing that despite his being an FRS etc. you never felt belittled by him and we had many a challenging discussion as he always made time for me, although it was inevitable that the discussions would end up on the subject of algae, his passion.

He was a fantastic cosupervisor for my student, Jenny Carfae and we all had challenges to overcome, but John was always there for us. He was great for bouncing round ideas with my Portuguese colleague Christina Cruz and we came very close to writing a new review together, thwarted by time it never got further than skeletal ideas sadly. Trying to resolve to what extent the different N forms drive reactions, versus pH.

I remember being given the job of editing his contribution to the New Phytologist. But John never assumed he knew best and was always open to suggestions, an inspirational kind man.